

Section 1: Demographic details of ASHA

Name:		Age:
Education level: Primary/Secondary/Higher Secondary/Graduate/Postgraduate		Marital Status: Married / Divorced / Widowed
Years of experience:		

Section 2: Job Satisfaction

Please indicate your level of satisfaction with the following aspects of your job by selecting the most appropriate response:

S no	Criteria	Question	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
1	Job Security	How satisfied are you with your job security?					
2.	Salary and Compensation	How satisfied are you with your incentives and compensation?					
3.	Workload	How satisfied are you with your current workload?					
4.	Work-Life Balance	How satisfied are you with your work-life balance?					
5.	Training and Professional Development	Are you satisfied with the training and professional development opportunities provided to you?					
6.	Relationships with Colleagues and Supervisors	How satisfied are you with your relationships with colleagues and supervisors?					
7.	Recognition and Appreciation	Do you feel adequately recognized and appreciated for your work?					
8.	Overall Job Satisfaction	Overall, how satisfied are you with your job as an ASHA worker?					

Section 3: Challenges Faced

3.1. Please rate the following challenges on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being "Not a challenge" and 5 being "Major Challenge."

S. no	Question	Not a Challenge	Minor Challenge	Moderate Challenge	Challenge	Major Challenge
1	Lack of training and resources					
2	Communication barriers with the community					
3	Cultural or social barriers in healthcare delivery					
4	Limited support from the healthcare system					

5	Safety concerns during fieldwork					
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Section 4: Open-Ended Questions

What aspects of your job do you find most satisfying, and why?

What aspects of your job do you find least satisfying, and why?

Section 4: Additional Comments

Please use this space to provide any additional comments or suggestions related to your job satisfaction or areas of improvement within your role as an ASHA worker.

